

NASA'S OCEANIC REMOTE SENSING PROGRAM:
AN IMPLEMENTATION APPROACH

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ABSTRACT - The combination of GEOS-3, NIMBUS, and SEASAT have clearly demonstrated a capability for observing the oceans from space, and have allowed us to begin to apply remotely acquired data to the solution of oceanographic problems. Accordingly, we are now pursuing the implementation of a satellite ocean observing capability at minimum cost. Whether this be by obtaining data from other sources, deploying ocean sensors piggyback on other satellites, or where absolutely essential, flying a dedicated ocean satellite, the intent is to demonstrate the potential for routinely making satellite observations of the ocean and to thereby pave the way for the operational agencies to implement satellite ocean observing systems in the future.

INTRODUCTION

The Earth's ocean has an important tempering effect on regional climates. Without the ocean, large areas of the earth on which we live would either be unbearably hot or cold compared to their present states, and life would be very different. Two processes are involved: first, the ocean currents carry over one-half the heat supply moving from the equator to the poles (the atmosphere carrying the remainder), thus greatly reducing the very large temperature contrast from higher to lower latitudes that would otherwise occur. Second, the large heat capacity of the sea greatly reduces seasonal temperature fluctuations, especially at higher latitudes, leading to the equable climate of our continent.

The ocean is important in a variety of other ways. It has been fished for food since prehistoric times and today

provides a large fraction of the world's food supply. The oceans carry the great fleets of commerce that move bulk commodities essential to modern society. We are becoming increasingly dependent on offshore facilities for provision of the fuel that our modern society demands. The movement of ocean water (usually called the general circulation) influences our planning for the disposal of radioactive wastes as well as the operational deployment of the Navy's sea based deterrent force.

However, the ocean is extremely difficult to observe, and is therefore poorly understood. It is a highly complex, global fluid, and unlike the atmosphere, there is no global observational system. In fact, traditional seagoing techniques yield observations infrequently and only over limited regions.

To improve our understanding of the global ocean, and thus to enable a more thorough assessment of its influence on the problems stated above, a global observational system is required. Given the global nature of the problem, and the difficulty of making measurements at sea, satellites alone offer the potential for addressing this need.

Thus, the overall goal of NASA's Oceanic Processes Program is to develop and evaluate the utility of spaceborne techniques for observing the oceans and to apply these techniques to advance our understanding of oceanic behavior. Although this goal is directed toward the fundamental scientific aspects of the oceans, many of the specific research questions being addressed by this program will, when answered, provide an improved capability for the utilization of spaceborne techniques for operational purposes.

This paper, then, presents NASA's long range plans for achieving this goal, and as such, represents summaries and/or extractions from internal NASA planning documents.

BACKGROUND

We have taken a preliminary look at the scientific requirements for viewing the oceans from space and find that they fall into the following three general areas: (1) studying the circulation (both geostrophic and wind-driven), heat content, and horizontal heat flux of the global oceans, how they are influenced by the atmosphere, and how they in turn influence climate; (2) studying the primary productivity of the oceans, how it is influenced by oceanic circulation and the atmosphere, and how it in turn influences the marine food chain, the rate of CO₂ uptake, and climate; and (3) studying the characteristics of sea ice, how they are influenced by the atmosphere and ocean, and how they in turn influence climate. These research areas thus form the general objectives of the Oceanic Processes Program.

In support of the first objective, oceanic circulation, we have seen the Ocean Topography Experiment (TOPEX) Science Working Group (Carl Wunsch, MIT, chairman) report published, demonstrating the feasibility of using satellite altimetry for determining ocean circulation. We are proposing the launch of TOPEX, carrying such an altimeter, in the late 1980's. We are also developing techniques for the removal of the directional ambiguity associated with scatterometer winds (and surface stress), as well as conducting quantitative studies with NASA's Global Weather Program to assess the impact of scatterometer winds on atmospheric forecasts. We are working on selected in situ sensors for the determination of ocean currents. Data from such sensors is necessary to evaluate the potential of spaceborne observations of surface currents, as well as provide complementary subsurface currents.

Regarding our second objective - the determination of global primary productivity - we are investigating the capabilities and limitations of spaceborne observations of chlorophyll concentrations (by the Coastal Zone Color Scanner (CZCS) on NIMBUS-7) to estimate phytoplankton productivity. We are also looking at in situ techniques for the measurement of both phyto- and zooplankton patchiness.

Finally, we have had success in the area of sea ice research using a microwave radiometer (SMMR) on NIMBUS-7 and SEASAT, and a synthetic aperture radar (SAR) on SEASAT. We are currently examining the full potential of the SMMR for unambiguously resolving the relative contributions made by first year and multi-year components to sea ice concentration images, and we are developing procedures for utilizing successive SAR images to quantify the movement of the sea ice field.

Given the definition of ocean science questions and corresponding satellite sensor performance specifications, we are concentrating on those sensors with the greatest near-term potential for contributing to our understanding of the fundamental behavior of the ocean. In order to minimize overall program cost, we are studying various flight options for those sensors - aboard a dedicated spacecraft if so constrained by deployment requirements, or aboard spacecraft-of-opportunity if deployment requirements are minimal. Moreover, we are looking to other sponsors of ocean-related spacecraft in those cases where their observations can meet our needs.

IMPLEMENTATION APPROACH

Ocean Topography Experiment (TOPEX)

The goal of TOPEX is to provide a basis for understanding the circulation of the global oceans. As a purely scientific endeavor, this goal is of great importance, for it will provide the first comprehensive, global insight into ocean circulation dynamics. Large scale movement of water in the oceans directly affects many aspects of life on earth: climate and its prediction, fishing, the movement and fate of pollutants, operation of commercial and naval vessels, and design and operation of offshore facilities.

An advanced microwave radar altimeter is the primary sensor aboard TOPEX. As has been demonstrated with earlier instruments aboard SKYLAB, GEOS-3, and SEASAT, an altimeter can measure the topography of the sea surface. Given sufficient knowledge of the geoid and the orbit of the satellite carrying the altimeter, it is possible to calculate surface geostrophic currents. Repeated realizations of the surface topography yield information on both the mean and variable components of those surface currents. (Even if the geoid is not known, it is still possible to calculate the variable surface

currents). Concurrent in situ measurements of subsurface currents enable the full three-dimensional structure of the geostrophic current field to be determined.

Just as the recently completed Global Weather Experiment focused on improving our understanding of the circulation of the atmosphere, a World Ocean Circulation Experiment (WOCE) is planned to similarly improve our understanding of the circulation of the oceans. Scheduled to begin in 1988 and extend for five years, WOCE presents a unique opportunity to obtain the complementary observations required to fully exploit the potential of satellite altimetry. Correspondingly, a TOPEX mission has been proposed that would have a three-year design life, with expendables for two additional years. In addition to the advanced radar altimeter, TOPEX will carry a microwave radiometer (for water vapor correction), and laser cubes and an advanced RF tracking system for precision orbit determination. A 1988 launch would enable TOPEX to fly concurrently with WOCE.

Scatterometer

Observations of surface winds can augment TOPEX in providing a basis for understanding the circulation of the global oceans. Upper-ocean currents, as well as surface waves, are generated by the stress exerted on the ocean surface by surface winds. As has been demonstrated with earlier instruments aboard aircraft and SEASAT, a scatterometer can measure the small-scale roughness of the sea surface, from which the associated wind velocity or stress can be calculated. Modern oceanographic measurements show that ocean currents are much more variable than previously known, and a capability to obtain scatterometer winds would permit calculation of time-dependent, wind-driven upper ocean currents. Knowledge of these currents, together with observations to be provided by TOPEX and WOCE, would allow for the first time a global determination of the ocean circulation - both wind-driven and geostrophic. Scatterometer winds would also enable improvements to be made in marine forecasts of wave conditions, the intensity and location of storms, etc.

A scatterometer is being proposed as a "piggyback" instrument. Possibilities for flight exist with TOPEX or on one of a number of other spacecraft-of-

opportunity such as the Navy's Remote Ocean Sensing System (ROSS) or Canada's RADARSAT. Coverage beginning in 1988 would allow maximum overlap with TOPEX and WOCE.

Ocean Color Imager (OCI)

An Ocean Color Imager measures near-surface chlorophyll concentrations, thereby allowing the determination of global primary productivity - the rate at which oceanic plants (phytoplankton) make energy available to the marine food chain. Consequently, these phytoplankton are of major importance to world fisheries. Productivity also determines the rate of CO₂ uptake from the atmosphere by the marine biosphere. As has been demonstrated by a similar instrument aboard NIMBUS-7 (the CZCS), a color imager offers a synoptic, global perspective for observing phytoplankton distribution and dynamics. This information has significance for world fisheries, biological (ecological) research, and waste disposal management. When combined with complementary in situ data, information derived from the OCI can be utilized to estimate primary productivity both globally and for specific regions.

Preliminary studies show that it is feasible to fly the OCI "piggyback" on the NOAA series of operational meteorological satellites, and we are working with NOAA to propose an OCI flight on NOAA-H in 1987. An overlap with the flight of TOPEX and a scatterometer would enable us to assess the influence of winds, waves, and currents on primary productivity.

Sea Ice Data System

Sea ice is the single most important factor influencing heat transfer between the ocean and atmosphere at high latitudes. Sea ice cover also provides an early indicator of changes in global temperature and sea level. Microwave radiometers flown aboard the NIMBUS series and the SAR aboard SEASAT have demonstrated a capability to provide information on ice cover and on ice movement/deformation, respectively on a global basis. A unique opportunity for receiving microwave radiometer data exists with the microwave radiometer (SSMI) being flown on the Air Force's series of meteorological satellites (DMSP) scheduled to fly from about 1984 through 1991. A similar opportunity for receiving SAR data exists with

European and Japanese satellites planned for the late 1980's. In order to implement a sea ice data system, DMSP/SSM/I data could be obtained from the Navy's facility in Monterey, California, and foreign SAR data could be obtained from a proposed Alaskan ground station. If we can gain access to data from instruments flown on spacecraft sponsored by groups other than NASA, and can establish appropriate data systems, we can satisfy our sea ice research needs without independently deploying these sensors.

Synthetic Aperture Radar

In the field of polar research, it has been demonstrated by SEASAT that a SAR has the capability to locate ice boundaries and openings with high precision (100 m.). Thus, with the repetitive coverage afforded by satellites, it is possible to monitor the motion and formation of the floating ice pack and thence determine the surface circulation of the polar basin. In addition, the sensor can be used to determine ice type and age. For oceanography, the sensor can be used to determine the ocean wave directional height spectrum and surface currents, both with high resolution. This knowledge is important in studies of the ocean circulation, as well as to commercial and operational interests.

NASA and Canada's Department of Energy, Mines, and Resources have been jointly pursuing the definition of mission requirements for a free-flying SAR (RADARSAT) since 1980. While the Canadian interest is largely in the area of ice, NASA's interest falls in the land, ice, and oceans areas about equally. The Canadians are looking towards a 1990 launch for RADARSAT and are very much interested in obtaining a cooperative arrangement with NASA. The options available range from a funding split with commensurate input to the establishment of mission goals and requirements, to NASA providing a launch and one or more companion sensors, the scatterometer being the most likely choice from an Oceans point of view.

Shuttle Payload Development

Given the need to obtain continuous ocean data over extensive periods (typically years), the role of Shuttle in our program appears principally to be that of a launch vehicle for our free-flying satellites. However, in those cases where we are developing new

technical capabilities for observing the oceans from space, the shuttle could be quite useful for demonstrating and evaluating those capabilities. Such a situation exists with the Ocean Microwave Package (OMP), which combines the features of a Wide-swath Interferometric Altimeter (WIA) with a Directional Wave Spectrometer (DWS). An aircraft version of the DWS has already been flown, and has demonstrated a unique technique for measuring the directional spectrum of ocean surface waves by a non-imaging, and therefore low data rate, method. The WIA is an altimeter with two antennas separated in the cross-track direction to form a cross-track interference pattern. Using this technique, it will be possible to measure cross-track topography (or sea surface slope) as well as the along-track slope provided by conventional single-beam altimeters. Knowledge of the cross-track slope will enable the direct determination of the direction of the ocean surface geostrophic current.

From an implementation point of view, the two techniques are extremely complementary and could most effectively be configured by sharing essential hardware items, thus reducing cost. The OMP is in the very early planning stages.

CONCLUSIONS

The benefits of remotely sensing the oceans from space have yet to be fully recognized, but it has become increasingly apparent that satellite oceanography has the potential to revolutionize our understanding of the oceans. With the demise of the National Oceanic Satellite System (NOSS), NASA has continued to vigorously pursue a research program in satellite oceanography. Given our planning for the dedicated deployment of the TOPEX altimetric spacecraft and the piggyback deployments of a scatterometer and color scanner, and assuming that we can negotiate access to other sources of ocean data as noted above, we believe that this research program will remain viable for years to come.

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